

Lipid profile and fatty acid composition in eggs of *Mugil parsia* in comparison with tissue lipid

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The lipid class and fatty acid composition in eggs of Indian estuarine *Mugil parsia* has been studied in comparison with body tissue lipid. The eggs contain about 7.8 times higher lipid than that of the body tissue. The major portion of lipid in eggs is composed of wax ester followed by triacylglycerol (TAG), phospholipid (PL) and cholesterol. But in the body tissue, the major fraction is TAG, wax ester, PL and cholesterol. Egg lipids are rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) of which major fractions are accumulated in PL fractions. The results of the study indicate that *M. parsia* eggs are rich in PUFA, which are very much important from nutritional point of view.

Mugil parsia (Hamilton Buchanes), popularly known as *parse* in Bengali, is one of the most common fishes available in India. The fish along with its eggs are utilized to prepare delicious dishes. Several marine and estuarine fish species are rich in n-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) such as eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) or docosahexaenoic acid (DHA). There is strong evidence suggesting that consumption of fish containing high level of these fatty acids is favorable for human health and has a particular beneficial effect in preventing cardiovascular diseases¹.

The research works of Indian freshwater and estuarine fish egg lipids and their biochemical and nutritional significance are scarce. The present study aims at investigating the lipid profiles of *M. parsia* eggs of Indian origin to find out whether the egg lipids contain any important fatty acids in significant proportions in comparison with the body tissue lipid, their nutritional significance on the basis of essential fatty acids present in neutral lipid and PL fractions.

Results and discussion

The lipid content and lipid class composition in eggs and body tissue of *M. parsia* are shown in Table 1. Mean wet weight of mature eggs (3.2 ± 0.8) accounts for 10.9% of total weight of fish. The lipid content in eggs and body tissue is about 44.5 and 5.7%, respectively on dry basis. The eggs contain about 7.8 times higher lipid than that of the body tissue. The major portion of lipid in eggs is composed of wax ester (about 51.2%) followed by TAG, PL and cholesterol (32.4, 13.6 and 4.1%, respectively). But in the body tissue, major fraction is TAG (about 86.6%) followed by wax ester (15.6%), PL (11.7%) and cholesterol (2.0%). Besides, trace amounts of fatty acids, monoglycerids and diglycerides are observed on the TLC plate.

Table 1. Lipid content and lipid class composition in eggs and body tissue of *M. parsia**

Total weight of fish (wet weight in g)	29.3 ± 2.6	
Weight of fish eggs (wet weight in g)	3.2 ± 0.6	
Moisture content in fish eggs (%)	47.9 ± 1.2	
Moisture content in body tissue (%)	54.4 ± 1.2	
Lipid content (% dry weight) in eggs	44.5 ± 3.2	
Lipid content (% dry weight) in tissue	5.7 ± 1.1	
	Eggs	Body tissue
Phospholipid	13.6 ± 1.0	11.7 ± 1.2
Cholesterol	4.1 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.4
Triacylglycerol	32.4 ± 1.2	71.6 ± 1.4
Wax ester	51.2 ± 2.4	15.6 ± 2.1

*Values are mean ± SE, n = 6.

Three major phospholipid fractions, viz. phosphatidyl choline (PC), phosphatidyl inositol (PI) and phosphatidyl ethanalamine (PE) were observed in eggs and body tissue of *M. parsia* (Table 2). Among the phospholipids, the most abundant is PC in all the six samples. PI content in the eggs is to some extent higher than that of body tissue. Besides, trace amount of phosphatidic acid and phosphatidylserine were also recorded in eggs and body tissue.

Table 2. Major phospholipid fractions (% of total phospholipid) in the eggs of *M. parsia**

	Eggs	Body tissue
Phosphatidyl choline	55.0 ± 3.8	62.1 ± 3.6
Phosphatidyl inositol	26.9 ± 2.4	22.1 ± 2.2
Phosphatidyl ethanalamine	18.1 ± 2.0	16.3 ± 1.4

*Values are mean ± SE, n = 6.

Table 3. Fatty acid composition in body tissue and eggs of *M. parsia**

Fatty acid	Fatty acid composition (% w/w)					
	Body Tissue			Eggs		
	Total	TAG	PL	Total	TAG	PL
14:0	6.6 ± 0.53	9.9 ± 0.43	0.4 ± 0.02	3.9 ± 0.41	5.5 ± 0.93	0.8 ± 0.09
16:0	31.4 ± 2.31	31.9 ± 0.86	2.9 ± 0.18	39.9 ± 0.72	48.7 ± 4.85	30.5 ± 3.2
18:0	4.7 ± 0.15	2.5 ± 0.12	7.6 ± 0.24	7.4 ± 1.37	1.7 ± 0.22	10.6 ± 0.20
20:0	0.5 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.11	0.1 ± 0.02	0.0	0.0	0.0
24:0	0.3 ± 0.05	0.4 ± 0.07	0.8 ± 0.02	0.6 ± 0.10	0.4 ± 0.09	0.7 ± 0.11
Total saturates	43.1 ± 0.62	45.2 ± 0.81	37.9 ± 0.32	51.9 ± 1.44	51.7 ± 3.37	39.6 ± 1.41
14:1	1.0 ± 0.15	1.9 ± 0.26	0.2 ± 0.01	0.8 ± 0.26	2.2 ± 0.24	0.8 ± 0.08
16:1	22.6 ± 0.33	28.8 ± 0.27	0.5 ± 0.03	12.9 ± 1.67	17.8 ± 3.59	2.7 ± 0.69
18:1	12.1 ± 0.31	11.2 ± 0.34	16.3 ± 0.14	14.1 ± 1.30	12.3 ± 1.77	8.8 ± 1.22
20:1	3.1 ± 0.22	2.6 ± 0.2	1.5 ± 0.03	3.4 ± 0.36	1.4 ± 0.30	0.8 ± 0.14
24:1	0.5 ± 0.04	0.2 ± 0.06	2.9 ± 0.04	0.4 ± 0.06	0.2 ± 0.07	1.3 ± 0.16
Total monounsaturat	39.2 ± 0.51	44.3 ± 0.68	21.5 ± 0.15	31.2 ± 1.78	33.7 ± 0.79	13.5 ± 0.70
16:2	1.8 ± 0.04	1.6 ± 0.16	0.6 ± 0.02	1.2 ± 0.20	1.1 ± 0.10	0.7 ± 0.44
18:2(n-6)	3.6 ± 0.42	1.7 ± 0.41	2.9 ± 0.60	3.6 ± 0.33	2.1 ± 0.36	2.1 ± 0.23
20:2(n-3)	0.8 ± 0.02	0.6 ± 0.07	0.8 ± 0.03	0.7 ± 0.06	0.6 ± 0.19	0.5 ± 0.10
20:4(n-3)	3.5 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.1	11.1 ± 0.11	1.9 ± 0.16	1.1 ± 0.30	6.4 ± 0.43
20:5(n-3)	6.0 ± 0.29	2.5 ± 0.29	12.1 ± 0.10	3.5 ± 0.47	1.1 ± 0.30	10.8 ± 1.43
22:5(n-3)	1.7 ± 0.04	1.12 ± 0.09	4.0 ± 0.09	2.9 ± 0.34	1.7 ± 0.16	5.3 ± 0.64
22:6(n-3)	1.7 ± 0.03	0.8 ± 0.02	8.7 ± 0.24	4.3 ± 0.22	2.1 ± 0.26	17.1 ± 2.04
Total PUFA	17.3 ± 0.81	9.1 ± 0.6	40.2 ± 0.18	17.1 ± 0.98	9.8 ± 0.78	46.9 ± 1.44
Total(n-3)	13.6 ± 0.42	5.8 ± 0.21	36.7 ± 0.15	12.8 ± 1.02	6.6 ± 0.50	44.2 ± 1.42
Total(n-6)	3.6 ± 0.42	1.7 ± 0.41	2.9 ± 0.06	3.6 ± 0.33	2.1 ± 0.36	2.1 ± 0.23
(n-3)/(n-6)	3.9 ± 0.40	3.4 ± 0.71	12.8 ± 0.25	3.7 ± 0.57	3.5 ± 0.92	21.7 ± 0.55

*Values are mean ± SE, n = 6

Fatty acid composition of total lipid, TAG and PL fractions in eggs and body tissue are shown in Table 3. Among saturated fatty acids most abundant is palmitic acid in both body tissue and eggs. The monoenoic fatty acids are represented by two major components, palmitoleic acid (16:1 n-7) and oleic acid (18:1 n-9). Arachidonic acid (AA, 20:4 n-6) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA, 22:6 n-3) in PL fraction in body tissue are 11.1 and 8.7% and in egg 6.4 and 17.1%, respectively

Analysis of lipid class composition in eggs of *M. parsia* revealed the presence of high level of wax esters. The fatty acid and fatty alcohol composition in wax esters are shown in Tables 4 and 5, respectively. Palmitic acid is predominant in the wax ester part (about 40.4% in eggs and 45.3% in body tissue) followed by stearic (12.8% in eggs and 15.4% in body tissue), oleic and higher unsaturated fatty acids. Some unidentified fatty acids were observed, expressed as other fatty acids. Among the fatty alcohols, the major one is 16:0 alcohol in both the egg lipid and the body tissue (about 75.2 and 82.2%, respectively).

Table 4. Fatty acid composition of wax esters*

Fatty acid	Eggs % (w/w)	Body tissue % (w/w)
14:0	4.0 ± 0.2	5.2 ± 0.4
16:0	40.4 ± 2.22	45.3 ± 2.1
16:1	9.1 ± 0.21	6.7 ± 0.54
18:0	12.8 ± 0.78	15.4 ± 0.32
18:1	11.1 ± 0.62	14.2 ± 1.1
18:2	2.2 ± 0.04	3.6 ± 0.82
20:0	2.4 ± 1.0	1.2 ± 0.02
20:4(n-3)	7.1 ± 1.67	2.3 ± 0.34
20:5(n-3)	2.1 ± 1.5	1.3 ± 0.21
22:5(n-3)	6.5 ± 1.8	2.2 ± 0.03
22:6(n-3)	2.1 ± 1.1	3.4 ± 1.2
Others		

*Values are mean ± SE, n = 6

Lipid is usually the primary form of energy stored in eggs and larvae in many fish species². In the rapid development of larvae lipid particularly TAG reserves can be used to obtain the necessary metabolic energy to enhance the development. In the present study lipid content in the eggs is much higher than that in the body tissue of which wax ester is the major fraction observed, which provides an important source of energy in addition to or in place of TAG³. Wax esters have also been observed in other marine fish species⁴.

Table 5. Fatty alcohol composition of wax esters

Fatty acid	Eggs % (w/w)	Body tissue % (w/w)
14:0	2.4 ± 1.2	2.1 ± 0.81
15:0	1.6 ± 0.52	1.6 ± 0.42
16:0	75.2 ± 4.21	82.2 ± 3.54
18:0	4.5 ± 0.5	5.4 ± 2.11
18:1	8.6 ± 1.3	3.1 ± 0.38
Others	7.7 ± 3.7	5.6 ± 0.32

*Values are mean ± SE, n = 6

A significant amount of PL is also present in the eggs of parse of which PC is predominant. PC is long been known for its structural role in eggs and is also implicated as a very important metabolic precursor in the eggs of larvae of many marine species⁵.

The health benefits of fish oils have been extensively investigated due to low incidence of coronary heart disease among populations who consume large amount of fish⁶. The active constituents of fish oil are mainly long chain n-3 fatty acids, EPA and DHA. Several marine fish species are rich in n-3 PUFAs. Compared with marine fish, freshwater fish contain higher level of C₁₈-PUFA and also substantial amount of EPA and DHA⁷. The presence of significant

amount of EPA and DHA (about 3.4% in body tissue and 7.2% in eggs) in *M. parsia* also supports these observations. The major portions of these fatty acids are accumulated in the PL fraction. *M. parsia* along with its eggs may be used as a very good source of essential fatty acids from nutritional point of view.

Experimental

Mature unfertilized eggs of *M. parsia* of six different gravid females weighing about 0.029 kg were collected during spawning season from local traders at Kolkata, West Bengal, India. The samples were stored in glass vials containing chloroform/methanol (2 : 1, v/v) having 0.01% (w/v) butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) at -20° prior to extraction.

The total lipid was extracted by the reported method⁸. After extraction, chloroform was removed under a stream of nitrogen and finally the lipid was dried under vacuum. The isolated lipid was mainly a mixture of PL, cholesterol, wax ester and TAG, identified on the TLC plate (silica gel G; solvent system, hexane/diethyl ether, 70 : 20, v/v) with phosphate stain, standard cholesterol and TAG. The PL and TAG were separated on a preparative TLC plate (20 cm × 20 cm) with the above solvent system, and the individual fractions were extracted with diethyl ether.

The total fatty acid composition of the lipid and of the isolated TAG and PL were determined by GLC method after derivatization into methyl esters⁹. The HP-5890A GLC (Hewlett Packard) was connected with a glass column (183 cm × 0.31 cm i.d.) packed with 10% diethylene glycol succinate (DEGS) supported on Chromosorb-WHP (100/200 mesh) of HP make. The oven, injector, detector block temperatures were maintained at 190, 230, and 240°, respectively. IOLAR-2 nitrogen (BOC India Ltd., India) was used as the carrier gas (flow rate 45 ml/min). The fatty acid ester peaks were identified and calibrated with standard methyl esters (Sigma). Total PL content was mea-

sured following standard method¹⁰. Individual PLs were measured by fractionation with two-dimensional TLC followed by phosphorus measurement.

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